

**Contribution of bacterial biodiversity on the operational performance of a styrene
biotrickling filter**

Kevin J. Portune, M. Carmen Pérez, Javier Álvarez-Hornos, and Carmen Gabaldón[#]

Research Group GI²AM, Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat de València,
Burjassot, Spain.

[#]Address correspondence to Carmen Gabaldón, carmen.gabaldon@uv.es

Research Group GI²AM, Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat de València, Av. De
la Universitat S/N, 46100, Burjassot, Spain.

Phone: +34 96 354 34 37

1 **Abstract**

2 Long-term operational stability of biotrickling filters (BTFs) degrading volatile organic
3 compounds (VOCs) is dependent on both physicochemical as well as biological
4 properties. Effects of increasingly stressful levels of air pollutants on the microbial
5 structure of biofilms within BTFs are not well understood, especially for VOCs such as
6 styrene. To investigate the relationship between biofilm biodiversity and operational
7 stability, the temporal dynamics of a biofilm from a biotrickling filter subjected to
8 stepwise increasing levels of air polluted with styrene was investigated using 16S rDNA
9 pyrosequencing and PCR-denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (PCR-DGGE). As
10 styrene contaminant loads were increased, microbial community composition was
11 distinctly altered and diversity was initially reduced in early stages but gradually
12 stabilized and increased diversity in later stages, suggesting a recovery and
13 acclimatization period within the microbial community during incremental exposure of
14 the pollutant. Although temporary reductions in known styrene-degrading bacterial
15 genera (*Pseudomonas* and *Rhodococcus*) occurred under increased styrene loads, stable
16 BTF performance was maintained due to functional redundancy. New candidate genera
17 for styrene degradation (*Azoarcus*, *Dokdonella*) were identified in conditions of high
18 styrene loads, and may have supported the observed stable BTF performance
19 throughout the experiment. Styrene inlet load was found to be important modulator of
20 community composition and may have been partly responsible for the observed
21 temporary reductions of *Pseudomonas*. Notable differences between dominant genera
22 detected via pyrosequencing compared to species detected by PCR-DGGE suggests that
23 simultaneous implementation of both techniques is valuable for fully characterizing
24 dynamic microbial communities.

25

26 **Keywords:**

27 biotrickling filter, microbial community, pyrosequencing, qPCR, styrene

28

29

30

31

32

33

34

35

36

37

38

39

40

41

42

43

44

45

46

47

48

49

50

51 **1 Introduction**

52 Increasing awareness of potential health and environmental hazards through the
53 release of industrially produced volatile organic compounds (VOCs) has led to tighter
54 regulations in VOC-producing factories in recent years. To offset the rising costs of
55 efficient disposal methods of VOCs, industries are increasingly exploring bioreactors as
56 cheaper and cost-effective alternatives. Air purifying bioreactors can vary in design
57 (biofilters, biotrickling filters, among others) (Iranpour et al., 2005) but most consist of
58 a reactor vessel filled with a solid packing material to provide support for the growth of
59 biofilms, which are responsible for the degradation and elimination of pollutant feed
60 sources. Biotrickling filters contain inorganic materials to which an organic inoculum
61 source must be added to provide the initial biotic component. In biotrickling filters,
62 water is uniformly sprayed over the packing material to form a liquid phase, which is
63 then recirculated over the column at continual or intermittent periods. Gaseous
64 pollutants are transferred to the liquid phase where they are then oxidized by
65 microorganisms that are present within the biofilms.

66 The central objective in the optimization of air biofiltration is identifying the
67 principal factors that can influence the stability of operational performance. The
68 efficiency of air biofiltration can be affected by operational factors, including inlet load,
69 empty bed residence time (EBRT), pH, temperature and nutrients, all of which can
70 affect microorganism survival and growth. Fully understanding the complex
71 interactions between microbial community dynamics and their responses to changes in
72 engineered ecosystems is essential for establishing and maintaining ecosystem stability
73 (Briones and Raskin, 2003). Acclimatization of the resident microbial populations to the
74 pollutant is highly dynamic, bioreactors operating conditions and contaminant loading
75 concentrations have been shown to heavily influence this acclimatization period (Cabrol

76 et al., 2012a). Also, shifts on microbial diversity in the initial operation resulted in a
77 significant different microbial community structure when purifying toluene than when
78 treating other seven sequentially VOCs in a lab-scale biofilter (Lu et al., 2018). By other
79 side, a comparative study under continuous or discontinuous conditions from the
80 beginning of the operation treating five aromatic compounds revealed that those genes
81 involved in biofilm formation were less active under discontinuous operation (Feng et
82 al., 2019); and differences in robustness levels of microbial communities among
83 different compounds with varying recalcitrance have also been observed in studies
84 using transient substrate pulses (Cabrol et al., 2012b) or by sequentially using different
85 aromatic pollutant combinations (Liao et al., 2018) . Although discontinuous operation
86 and changes or transient pulses of pollutants may reflect fluctuations commonly found
87 in industrial facilities, an extensive examination of how biofilms can respond and adapt
88 to gradually increasing stressful conditions needs to be evaluated. Therefore, stepwise
89 increases of inlet loads in carefully controlled laboratory settings allow the examination
90 of microbial community adaptation and evolution under increasingly stressful
91 physicochemical conditions.

92 Styrene is an organic compound and precursor to polystyrene, which is an
93 important component used in many industrial goods such as packaging materials and
94 plastic containers. Due to styrene's highly volatile and potentially toxic nature, release
95 of styrene gas to the environment requires proper management and disposal methods.
96 Although many bacterial isolates have demonstrated a capacity to utilize styrene as an
97 energy and carbon source (Hartmans et al., 1990), most research on styrene-degrading
98 microorganisms has focused primarily on a few bacterial genera including
99 *Pseudomonas* spp. (Beltrametti et al., 1997; Iwanade et al., 2005; Jang et al., 2005; Jang
100 et al., 2006; Okamoto et al., 2003), *Rhodococcus* spp. (Jung and Park, 2005; Warhurst et

101 al., 1994), *Xanthobacter* (Hartmans et al., 1989), and *Brevibacillus* (Hwang et al., 2008)
102 as well as several yeast strains (Cox et al., 1997; Qi et al., 2002; Rene et al., 2011).
103 Among studies examining the application of bacteria to degrade styrene emissions by
104 air biofiltration, most have employed monocultures or only several selected bacterial
105 groups as the inoculum for the biological component of bioreactors (Hwang et al., 2008;
106 Iwanade et al., 2005; Jang et al., 2004; Jang et al., 2005; Jang et al., 2006; Jung and
107 Park, 2005; Okamoto et al., 2003) or examined the effects of a complex community
108 inoculum (i.e. activated sludge) source in bioreactors degrading styrene (Pérez et al.,
109 2015). However, systematic increases in styrene levels and subsequent acclimation
110 responses of the biofilms still remain to be determined in biofiltration studies.

111 This study measured the temporal dynamics and acclimatization of microbial
112 biofilms from a biotrickling filter degrading styrene air emissions undergoing stepwise
113 increases of the concentration pollutant during a long-term operation period. In-depth
114 analysis of the bacterial community and composition was carried out using
115 pyrosequencing, and complementarily molecular tools such as denaturing gradient gel
116 electrophoresis (DGGE) and quantitative PCR (qPCR) were applied for comparative
117 purpose. In addition, the relationship between the operational parameters (inlet load,
118 nutrient content, EBRT and pH) and the microbial ecology was investigated.

119

120 **2 Materials and methods**

121 **2.1 Biotrickling filter operation conditions and sample collection**

122 A biotrickling filter (BTF) was constructed with a 20 L methacrylate column
123 (14.4 cm internal diameter, 123 cm bed length) packed with polypropylene rings (25
124 mm nominal diameter, specific surface area of $207 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-3}$, 71 kg m^{-3} bulk density, 92%
125 void fraction) (Flexiring, Koch-Glitsch B.V.B.A., Belgium). Along the length of the

126 column, two gas sampling ports at 0, and 123 cm from the inlet port located at the
127 bottom of the BTF facilitated measurements of styrene gas concentrations, while a
128 sampling port located at 20 cm from the inlet port were used for biofilm collection using
129 sterile spatulas. Compressed air was pumped through a mass flow controller
130 (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, The Netherlands) to adjust the EBRT. The air then mixed with
131 styrene supplied through a syringe pump (New Era, infusion/withdraw NE 1000 model,
132 New York, USA). The styrene/air mixture entered the BTF at the bottom of the column
133 and exited the cylinder through an outlet gas line at the top of the column. The BTF was
134 equipped with a recirculation tank that was used to intermittently feed the recirculation
135 solution into the bioreactor via countercurrent mode with respect to the air flow using a
136 centrifugal pump (2.5-3 L min⁻¹ for 15 min every 2 h). A nutrient solution (9.7 g NH₄Cl
137 L⁻¹, 0.9 g MgSO₄·7H₂O L⁻¹, 2.2 g (NH₄)₂HPO₄ L⁻¹, 0.5 g NaHCO₃ L⁻¹, 0.4 g NaOH L⁻¹,
138 0.6 g KCl L⁻¹ and Ca, Fe, Zn, Co, Mn, Na, Ni, B, I, Se, Cr, Cu and vitamins at trace
139 doses, buffered at pH 8) was supplied to the recirculation tank using a peristaltic pump.
140 The flow rate was maintained at a mass ratio of carbon to nitrogen of 25 (corresponding
141 to a flow rate of nutrients between 32 and 160 mL d⁻¹) in order to assure that the
142 nitrogen in the recirculation solution was not limiting.

143 At the start of the experiment, the BTF was inoculated with 1 L of activated
144 sludge from a municipal wastewater treatment plant (located in Quart-Benager,
145 Valencia, Spain) and was continuously recirculated over the bed for 24 h. The BTF was
146 operated at 22°C under continuous styrene loading for >5 months. A start-up period was
147 conducted for 20 days at the beginning of the experiment using styrene inlet loads of 13
148 g m⁻³ h⁻¹ and an EBRT of 60 s. After, six different stages with inlet loads within 17–29
149 g m⁻³ h⁻¹ and EBRTs within 30–60 s were applied.

150

151 **2.2 Analytical methods**

152 Styrene gas concentrations were measured daily at the inlet and outlet sampling
153 ports using a total hydrocarbon analyzer (Nira Mercury 901, Spirax Sarco, Spain). The
154 response factor of the total hydrocarbon analyzer was determined by a gas
155 chromatograph (model 7890, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) equipped with a
156 1 mL automated gas valve injection system and a flame ionization detector and a Rtx®-
157 VMS capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 1.4 µm). Helium was used as the carrier gas
158 at a flow rate of 1.3 mL min⁻¹. Temperatures of the injector, oven and detector were
159 250°C, 100°C and 240°C, respectively.

160 The pH of the recirculating solution was monitored daily using a pH/Cond 340i
161 multimeter (WTW, Germany). Twice per week, volatile suspended solids (VSS), anions
162 (nitrate, phosphate, sulfate and chloride) and cations (ammonium, sodium, potassium,
163 calcium and magnesium) were analyzed using an 883 Basic IC Plus Ionic
164 Chromatograph (Metrohm, Gomersoro S.A., Madrid, Spain).

165

166 **2.3 Nucleic acid isolation and 16S rDNA 454 pyrosequencing**

167 Samples from biofilms for microbial analysis were taken on the last day of the
168 start up period and each of the 6 stages (days 20, 45, 67, 87, 109, 133, and 155) before
169 the change of operational conditions for each respective stage. DNA extraction, 16S
170 rDNA amplification, and 454 pyrosequencing and analysis using the software program
171 mothur (Schloss et al., 2009) were carried out as described in Portune et al. (2015).

172 Samples were multiplexed using barcoded primers and all samples from each of the 7
173 time points were run in a single pyrosequencing run. A dendrogram for assessing
174 similarity between communities of different time points was created via the tree.shared
175 command within mothur using a distance matrix that was calculated using the Bray-

176 Curtis dissimilarity on a shared OTU file and then used in hierarchical clustering by the
177 unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) algorithm.

178

179 **2.4 Statistical analysis**

180 In order to visualize variation in community structure with distance, non-metric
181 multidimensional scaling (NMDS) was conducted in R, version 3.31 (Team, 2016).

182 Using a shared OTU file, a distance matrix was produced by the `veg.dist` command in
183 the R package `vegan` version 2.0-10 (Oksanen et al., 2013) using the Bray-Curtis
184 dissimilarity. The NMDS was created by the `isoMDS` function in the R package `MASS`
185 (Venables et al., 2002) using 2 selected dimensions.

186 To examine the relationship between microbial community structure and
187 different BTF physicochemical parameters, a canonical correspondence analysis (CCA)
188 was conducted using the R package `vegan` (Oksanen et al., 2013). Inlet load, nitrate,
189 phosphate, sulfate and magnesium were chosen as the BTF physicochemical parameters
190 to include in the model since the average values of these parameters varied across time
191 points and thus could have had an impact on bacterial community structure and
192 composition. Average values for environmental variables for each time point and
193 abundances of bacterial genera were $\log_{10}(x+1)$ transformed prior to analysis with CCA.
194 Significance of the CCA model and explanatory variables was tested using permutation
195 tests (999 permutations) from the `vegan` package.

196

197 **2.5 Quantitative Real-Time PCR (qPCR)**

198 In order to validate the results of the relative abundances of *Pseudomonas* spp.
199 detected by pyrosequencing, quantitative PCR (qPCR) was employed using
200 *Pseudomonas* genus-specific primers Pse435F (5'-ACTTTAAGTTGGGAGGAAGGG-

201 3′) and Pse686R (5′-ACACAGGAAATTCCACCACCC-3′) (Bergmark et al., 2012).
202 Plasmid standards containing the target region were first generated for the primer sets
203 Pse435F/Pse686R and Eub338F/Eub518R (general Eubacterial primers) using genomic
204 DNA extracted from cultures of a strain of the bacteria *Pseudomonas putida* isolated
205 from the BTF. PCR was carried out in a MyGene L Series Peltier thermal cycler
206 (LongGene Scientific Instruments, Hangzhou) where each respective primer pair was
207 used in separate 20 µL reactions consisting of final concentrations of 1X ExTaq buffer
208 (Takara), 0.2mM dNTPs, 0.5µM each respective primer pair, 0.5 units of ExTaq
209 (Takara), and the remaining volume with nuclease free molecular biology grade water
210 (Fisher). Final concentrations of each primer pair were experimentally optimized to
211 obtain the highest specificity of the amplification. PCR cycling conditions for the
212 *Pseudomonas* genus-specific gene consisted of 95°C for 5 min, followed by 30 cycles
213 of 95°C for 60 s, 60°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 30 s, and a final extension at 72°C for 10
214 min. Cycling conditions using the Eub338F/Eub518R primer set were the same except
215 an annealing temperature of 55°C was used instead. PCR amplicons were examined by
216 gel electrophoresis to confirm the specificity of the reaction by observing a single
217 amplified band with the correct expected size. Amplicons were purified using a High
218 Pure PCR Product Purification kit (Roche) and cloned using a TOPO TA cloning kit
219 (Life Technologies). Plasmids were isolated using a PureLink Quick Plasmid Miniprep
220 kit (Life Technologies S. A., Alcobendas, Spain) and the DNA concentrations were
221 determined by PicoGreen fluorometry (Molecular Probes, Life Technologies). qPCR
222 was then carried out using a StepOne™ Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems)
223 using SYBR™ Green PCR Master Mix and primer sets Pse435F/Pse686R and
224 Eub338F/Eub518R (final concentrations of 0.1 µM and 0.25 µM, respectively) for
225 detecting *Pseudomonas* spp. and general eubacteria, respectively. Cycling conditions

226 for the Pse435F/Pse686R primer set consisted of 95°C for 10 min, followed by 40
227 cycles of 95°C for 15 s, 60°C for 60 s, followed by a melting curve analysis. Similar
228 conditions were used for the Eub338F/Eub518R primer set except the annealing
229 temperature was changed to 55°C. Standard curves were generated using triplicate 10-
230 fold serial dilutions of each respective plasmid DNA and calculations of target copy
231 number were performed as described in Fierer et al. (2005). Relative fractional
232 abundances of *Pseudomonas* spp. were calculated as the ratio between the
233 *Pseudomonas*-specific copy numbers versus the general Eubacterial copy numbers.

234

235 **2.6 Denaturing Gradient Gel Electrophoresis (DGGE)**

236 Extracted DNA from samples from each of the 7 time points described above
237 was amplified by PCR using the primers 341F with a 40 bp GC clamp (5'-
238 CGCCCGCCGCGCGCGGGCGGGGCGGGGGCACGGGGGGCCTACGGGAG
239 GCAGCAG-3') (Muzyer et al., 1993) and 907R (5'-CCGTCAATTCMTTGTGAGTTT-
240 3') (Muzyer et al., 1998) targeting the 16S rRNA gene. Reactions consisted of 50 µL
241 volumes with final concentrations of 1X ExTaq PCR buffer, 0.2 mM dNTPs, 0.5 µM
242 forward and reverse primers, and 0.75 units of ExTaq DNA polymerase (Takara Bio,
243 Ōtsu, Shiga, Japan). PCR cycling conditions consisted of 94°C for 5 min, followed by
244 20 cycles of 94°C for 60 s, a touchdown annealing step of 0.5°C decreasing increments
245 for every cycle starting at 65°C for 30 s, and an extension of 72°C for 60 s, followed by
246 10 cycles of 94°C for 60 s, 65°C for 30 s, 72°C for 60 s, and a final extension at 72°C
247 for 10 min. Separation of PCR amplicons by DGGE was carried out using a KuroGEL
248 2020Y-DGGE system (VWR International Eurolab S. L.) using 6% (v/v)
249 polyacrylamide gels and a denaturant gradient of 30-55%. The definition of a 100%
250 denaturing solution consists of 7 M urea and 40% formamide. Electrophoresis was

251 performed at 100 V for 15 hours in 1X TAE buffer at 60°C. DGGE gels were stained
252 with the nucleic acid-binding reagent EuroSafe (EuroClone, Milan, Italy) and visualized
253 using a MiniBIS Pro transilluminator (DNR Bio-Imaging Systems Ltd., Jerusalem,
254 Israel). DGGE bands were excised with sterile scalpels and placed in 30 µl sterilized
255 Milli-Q water, then the polyacrylamide gels for each band were physically crushed
256 using a sterile pipet tip. Solutions were frozen overnight, centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for
257 2 minutes, then the supernatant was removed and 2 µL was used in a new PCR
258 according to the conditions previously described above. Isolated DGGE bands were
259 compared to the original BTF samples in order to confirm correct positioning and
260 appearance of a single band. Remaining PCR products were purified using a High Pure
261 PCR Product Purification Kit (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) and bi-directionally
262 sequenced on a 3730X DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies S.A.).
263 Taxonomic classification was carried out using the RDP Classifier (Wang et al., 2007)
264 and NCBI's Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) (Altschul et al., 1990).
265 Accession number PRJEB22918 contains all sequences of the pyrosequencing runs that
266 were deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) database
267 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/data/view/PRJEB22918>).

268 **3 Results**

269 **3.1 Biotrickling filter performance**

270 Full evaluation of the BTF performance was described elsewhere (Pérez et al.,
271 2015). In the work presented here, average values (mean ± standard deviation) of BTF
272 performance and actual operational conditions were calculated for the BTF start-up
273 period and six experimental stages (Table 1). After an initial start-up period of 20 days
274 where the BTF inoculum was acclimated to a low styrene inlet load and concentration
275 (13.0 ± 0.8 g styrene $\text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$, 216 ± 14 mg Nm^{-3} , respectively), the styrene inlet load was

276 incrementally increased over three stages to 26.6 ± 2.3 g styrene $\text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$, while
277 maintaining an empty bed residence time (EBRT) of 60 seconds. During stage four, the
278 EBRT was decreased to 45 seconds while maintaining the same styrene inlet load,
279 whereas the load was increased during stage 5 to yield the highest styrene inlet
280 concentration (512 mg Nm^{-3}). During the sixth and final stage, the EBRT was reduced
281 to 30 seconds and the inlet load was reduced to values similar to stage 2. Removal
282 efficiencies during the start-up period reached $>90\%$, but dropped to average stable
283 values between $74.7 \pm 6.4\%$ and $82.0 \pm 4.2\%$ during stage 2 through stage 6.
284 Elimination capacities ranged from 11.8 ± 1.4 g styrene $\text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$ at the start of the
285 experiment to 31.8 ± 2.1 g styrene $\text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$ during stage 5. The dissolved nitrate (NO_3^-),
286 calcium (Ca^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{2+}) were detected in concentrations of 99.1, 23.4 and
287 7.0 mg L^{-1} , respectively, during the startup period; but were substantially reduced
288 during the remaining time points of the experiment. The high average concentration of
289 these elements during first weeks could be attributed to their presence in the inoculum
290 (concentrations on day 0 of 42.6, 44.0 and 12.9 mg L^{-1} of NH_4^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} in the
291 recirculation solution, respectively). Ammonium (NH_4^+), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), sodium
292 (Na^+) and chloride (Cl^-) were maintained at relatively high stable levels during the
293 course of the experimental stages. The percentage of volatile suspended solids (VSS)
294 was maintained in stable values within 76.9–88.1%.

295

296 **3.2 Bacterial community analysis by pyrosequencing and qPCR**

297 The pyrosequencing run yielded between 10,990 and 15,708 raw reads for the 7
298 sampling time points (Table 2). Using the lowest number of normalized sequences for
299 all samples (10,464), a range from 376 to 378 OTUs were detected in the early
300 experimental stages up to 67 days, but this range dropped to 257 at the end of stage 5

301 when styrene inlet concentrations were at their highest levels. Bacterial diversity indices
302 Inverse Simpson and Shannon's diversity revealed that moderate diversity measures
303 were found during the beginning (20 days) and end (133, 155 days) of the experiment,
304 while the lowest diversity measurements were detected during days 67, 87 and 109. The
305 highest diversity measures were detected at 45 days. Evenness measures were consistent
306 across all sampling time points except for an elevated value detected at 45 days.

307 Dendrograms generated by the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity revealed a clear change
308 in bacterial composition over time as samples from the early time points (days 20, 45)
309 clustered together while the middle (days 67, 87 and 109) and late time points (days 133
310 and 155) demonstrated higher similarity to each other, respectively (Fig. 1). NMDS
311 analysis revealed a large separation between the first and last 2 time points compared to
312 the intermediate time points (i.e. 67, 87, 109 days) along the first ordination axis, while
313 separations between the first four time points compared to later time points was
314 observed along the second ordination axis (Fig. S1).

315 The highest percentages of bacterial sequences that could be classified to known
316 genera across all time points were assigned to *Hydrogenophaga* (Fig. 2). Among the top
317 25 classified genera, *Brevundimonas*, *Pseudoxanthomonas* and *Stenotrophomonas* were
318 detected in high relative abundances during the start of the experiment (26.2%, 7.4%
319 and 4.1% of total sequences, respectively), but steadily decreased over the course of the
320 experimental stages, while the reverse trend was observed for the genus *Azoarcus*. Both
321 *Rhodococcus* and *Pseudomonas* were detected in high percentages of total bacteria at
322 the start (6.6% and 15.6% of total sequences, respectively) and end of the experimental
323 stages (10.7% and 11.1% of total sequences, respectively), while *Pseudomonas*
324 decreased substantially during time points at 67, 87 and 109 days. *Achromobacter*
325 abundance also declined from the first stages (up to 2.1% of total sequences) from time

326 point 67 days on (<0.4% of total sequences). High percentages of unclassified bacteria
327 at the genera level were detected at 67 and 87 days. The majority of these unclassified
328 sequences displayed sequence similarity to the *Xanthomonadaceae* family at bootstrap
329 confidence estimates below 50% using the RDP classifier, with up to 23.2% and 22.7%
330 of total sequences found at 67 and 87 days, respectively (data not shown). A substantial
331 percentage of unclassified sequences also showed sequence similarity to the family
332 *Comamonadaceae* at bootstrap confidence estimates below 50%, ranging from 0.9% to
333 5.7% of the total sequences among different time points (data not shown). At the family
334 level, the *Comamonadaceae* and *Xanthomonadaceae* families made up the dominant
335 members, followed by *Caulobacteraceae*, *Nocardiaceae* and *Pseudomonadaceae* (Fig.
336 S2). The majority of total bacterial sequences that could be assigned to a known phylum
337 were classified as belonging to Proteobacteria, with percentages ranging from 67% to
338 81% across the seven time points (Fig. S3). Other dominant phyla that were detected in
339 abundances of up to 10% of total sequences during the course of the treatment period
340 include *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Firmicutes* and *Spirochaetes*.

341 In order to confirm the observed trend of the sharp reduction of the genus
342 *Pseudomonas* from time points at 67, 87 and 109 days, qPCR was employed using
343 *Pseudomonas* genus-specific primers. The average percentage of the total eubacterial
344 copies that could be attributed to *Pseudomonas* was then calculated. qPCR results
345 confirmed the observed pyrosequencing results of a sharp reduction of *Pseudomonas* to
346 levels less than 1% of the total observed bacteria during stages 2-4 (day 67 to day 109)
347 with subsequent increases during stages 5 and 6 (day 133 and day 155) achieving
348 average percentages up to 15% (Fig. 3).

349
350

3.3 Bacterial community by DGGE

Numerous bacterial species belonging to the phylum Bacteroidetes were detected, with *Chitinophaga pinensis*, *Galbibacter mesophilus*, *Cytophaga xylanolytica*, *Solitalea koreensis* and *Leadbetterella byssophila* among dominant members found in mid- to late experimental stages with high styrene levels (Table S1, Fig. 4, bands 1, 6, 7, 9, 10). *Hydrogenophaga sp. (defluvii or atypica)*, band 15) was detected in high abundances at each experimental stage, particularly during late stages with high styrene levels. Other prominent bacteria belonging to the phylum Proteobacteria detected in high abundances during late experimental stages with high styrene levels include *Azoarcus communis*, *Xenophilus azovorans* and *Paucibacter toxinivorans* (bands 12, 13, 14, respectively). Similar trends between bacterial species detected by DGGE and pyrosequencing profiles of respective bacterial genera over the experimental stages include *Hydrogenophaga*, *Azoarcus*, *Paracoccus*, *Spirochaeta* and *Rhodococcus* (Figs 2 and 4, bands 15, 12, 16, 18, 19, 20, respectively). Furthermore, similar trends observed in DGGE profiles for the species *Dokdonella immobilis* (Fig. 4, band 17) were found between a large portion of sequences in the unclassified genera at day 67 from pyrosequencing that were found to be taxonomically similar to *Dokdonella* (family *Xanthomonadaceae*) although they couldn't be assigned to this genus at the designated 50% bootstrap cutoff (data not shown).

3.4 Relationship between operational conditions and taxonomy

Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) was used to examine the relationships between microbial community structure and BTF physicochemical parameters. Permutation analysis revealed that the overall CCA model and explanatory variable

375 styrene inlet load was significant ($p < 0.05$), and highly correlated with CCA1 (Fig. 5).
376 The first two axes of the CCA accounted for 51% of the constrained inertia.
377 Several bacterial genera from the top 25 most abundant groups (from Fig. 2) were
378 correlated with increasing styrene inlet load including *Hydrogenophaga*, *Spirochaeta*,
379 *Shinella*, *Aquimonas* and *Azoarcus*. Several bacterial genera, including *Azoarcus*,
380 *Luteimonas*, *Desulfovibrio*, *Stappia* and *Spirochaeta* were correlated with high
381 phosphate concentration, while *Achromobacter* showed opposite effect. Few bacterial
382 genera including *Brevundimonas*, *Pseudoxanthomonas* and *Stenotrophomonas* were
383 correlated with increasing concentrations of sulfate and nitrate while *Pseudomonas* and
384 *Gp4* were correlated with increasing concentrations of magnesium and nitrate.

385 **4 Discussion**

386 Under steady-state conditions in bioreactors where operational parameters are
387 held constant, microbial diversity and composition of biofilms has been found to be
388 highly stable (Falk et al., 2009). In contrast, other studies observed substantial shifts in
389 microbial community composition in biofilters undergoing steady-state operation,
390 whereas no differences in bacterial diversity were observed (Cabrol et al., 2012a;
391 Nadarajah et al., 2007). When operational parameters of bioreactors (i.e. contaminant
392 load, temperature, nutrients) are altered, microbial community structure and diversity
393 has been observed to be highly dynamic (Miura et al., 2007; Nadarajah et al., 2007;
394 Portune et al., 2015). In this study, microbial community composition and diversity was
395 stable during both the start-up phase and stage 1, but radically changed during stage 2 as
396 averaged styrene inlet loads and inlet concentrations were subsequently increased to
397 $23.5 \pm 0.8 \text{ g styrene m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $391 \pm 13 \text{ mg Nm}^{-3}$, respectively. Clustering and NMDs
398 analysis further revealed a gradual evolution of community composition after stage 2,
399 with mid- and later time points grouping together, during which operational conditions

400 were continually more stressful (i.e. higher styrene inlet loads, inlet concentrations).
401 Microbial diversity also sharply dropped during stage 2 and remained low during stages
402 3 and 4, after which diversity began to increase again in the later stages. These patterns
403 suggest a recovery and acclimatization period in the microbial community structure as
404 bacterial composition and diversity were initially largely affected by the rising styrene
405 contaminant concentrations but eventually became stable after stage 4, even after
406 styrene inlet concentrations/loads were increased to the highest levels during stage 5. In
407 studies where bacterial communities were exposed to repeated shock loads of
408 contaminants over time, similar results were observed in which biofilms that were close
409 to the inlet contaminant sources became accustomed to high concentrations of
410 contaminants and microbial communities were thus relatively unaffected by pulses of
411 high contaminant loads (Cabrol et al., 2012b). Interestingly, even as styrene inlet
412 loads/concentrations in this study were substantially reduced along with a reduction in
413 EBRT during the final stage 6, bacterial composition and diversity were largely similar
414 to that observed in stage 5. This indicates that the bacterial composition within the
415 biofilm had reached a stable equilibrium and was relatively unaffected by varying
416 styrene levels.

417 Changes in individual bacterial groups were observed and followed very
418 different trends depending on the phylotype. Pyrosequencing and DGGE analysis
419 revealed the bacterial genera *Hydrogenophaga*, *Azoarcus*, *Spirochaeta* and the well-
420 known styrene-degrading genus *Rhodococcus* to be prominent genera that increased in
421 abundance as styrene inlet load and inlet concentrations were increased.

422 *Hydrogenophaga* spp. have been previously isolated from activated sludge and
423 wastewater (Kampfer et al., 2005; Yoon et al., 2008) and *Azoarcus* has been identified
424 as a dominant member in coking wastewater treatment plants (Ma et al., 2015).

425 Recently, our group identified both *Azoarcus* and *Hydrogenophaga* as dominant
426 members of the bacterial community in biofilters treating high styrene emissions
427 (Portune et al., 2015). Genes for styrene monooxygenase, which encodes the first
428 enzyme in the pathway for styrene degradation, have been identified in ENSEMBL
429 (Kersey et al., 2016) for both *Hydrogenopha* sp. T4 and several *Azoarcus* sp., thus
430 supporting their probable role as instrumental bacterial groups responsible for styrene
431 degradation in this study. The large percentages of unclassified sequences at the genera
432 level assigned to the *Xanthomonadaceae* family at days 67 and 87 in this experiment
433 suggest a prominent role in styrene degradation for specific groups from this family.
434 According to our DGGE results, *Dokdonella immobilis*, from the family
435 *Xanthomonadaceae*, may in fact be the bacterial species that is represented by these
436 unclassified sequences as this species was found to be a dominant bacterial species at
437 both days 67 and 87. As *Dokdonella immobilis* sp. has been previously isolated from a
438 batch reactor treating other aromatic compounds such as triphenylmethane (Liu et al.,
439 2013), this species is a likely new candidate for styrene degradation. In a previous
440 study, Arnold et al. (1997) identified several bacterial isolates including the genera
441 *Tsukamurella*, *Sphingomonas*, *Xanthomonas* and *Pseudomonas* with styrene
442 degradation capability. In this study, both *Tsukamurella* and *Sphingomonas* were found
443 in low abundances but did not appear to positively respond to increasing styrene
444 concentrations. The substantial decrease of *Pseudomonas* bacteria only on stage 2 to 4
445 cannot be explained by the increase of styrene concentrations; for example,
446 *Pseudomonas putida* has been shown capable of growing in media culture containing
447 more than 50% (v/v) toluene and high concentrations of cyclohexane, xylene, styrene
448 and heptanol (Inoue and Horikoshi, 1989). According to the canonical analysis (Fig. 5)
449 *Pseudomonas* abundance was correlated with increasing nitrate and magnesium

450 concentration, a possible explanation for the sharp decrease of its abundance on stages 1
451 to 4 could be the development of anoxic/anaerobic microenvironments within the
452 biofilm. The activity of the sulfate-reducing *Desulfovibrio* species (a well-known
453 anaerobic aerotolerant species) along with the fast reduction of nitrate from stage 2
454 points to some limitation of oxygen availability within the biofilm. Furthermore, the
455 bacterial genera *Brevundimonas* and *Achromobacter*, which appeared to be important
456 degraders of styrene (Portune et al., 2015; Liao et al, 2018) were substantially reduced
457 under increasing concentrations of styrene in this study. However, it is unclear whether
458 other factors may have influenced the decline of these bacterial genera. From the
459 canonical analysis (Fig. 5) the progressive decline of *Achromobacter* genus abundance
460 seems to be correlated to the lowest phosphate concentrations observed at the beginning
461 of the experiment (stages 1 and 2). Whereas the decline of *Brevundimonas* genus can be
462 related not only to the low nitrate concentrations from stage 1 on (as in the case of
463 *Pseudomonas*), but also to the concomitant reduction of sulfate, as its abundance was
464 correlated with increasing concentrations of nitrate and sulfate (Fig 5). Other novel
465 bacterial genera identified through pyrosequencing and DGGE analysis that are
466 potentially associated with styrene degradation include *Aquimonas*, *Spirochaeta*,
467 *Shinella*, *Fusibacter*, *Roseateles*, *Stappia*, *Xenophilus*, *Chitinophaga* and *Solitalea*.
468 However, as no genetic information is currently known regarding styrene degradation
469 pathways in these organisms, confirmation of styrene degradation ability is still needed
470 in cultured experiments.

471 Depending on their responses to environmental disturbances in the context of
472 ecosystem processes, microbial communities can be characterized as resistant, resilient
473 or exhibiting functional redundancy (Allison and Martiny, 2008). Resistance occurs
474 when microbial community composition remains unchanged in the face of a

475 disturbance; resilience is when the microbial composition is altered by the disturbance
476 but returns to the original composition over time; and functional redundancy is
477 characterized by a microbial composition that remains altered but performs ecosystem
478 processes similar to the original community. The continual changes in microbial
479 composition observed throughout the experimental stages in this study suggest that the
480 microbial population was neither resistant nor resilient to the disturbances of stepwise
481 increasing styrene loads. Poor structural resistance capacity for microbial populations is
482 well-described in gas biofiltration communities as well as wastewater ecosystems and
483 soils (reviewed in Cabrol and Malhautier, 2011). However, BTF performance in this
484 study (i.e. RE and EC) remained relatively stable from stage 2 until the end of the
485 experiment, despite reductions in well-known styrene degrading bacterial genera
486 including *Pseudomonas* and to some extent *Brevundimonas* and *Rhodococcus* during
487 the stages 2-4, suggesting some degree of functional redundancy from the population
488 after stage 1. Functional redundancy is a common feature found in numerous types of
489 bioreactor and wastewater environments (Ayarza et al., 2010; Cabrol et al., 2012a;
490 Fernandez et al., 1999; Franklin and Mills, 2006; Zumstein et al., 2000). Although
491 styrene catabolism has been demonstrated only in a few select bacterial species, it is
492 probable that uncharacterized bacterial groups that have the ability to oxidize styrene
493 were instrumental in maintaining operational stability observed here. New bacterial
494 candidates for styrene degradation have been proposed (see above) and new styrene-
495 degrading species are likely to be identified in the future as studies with high throughput
496 sequencing techniques become more common. Furthermore, in addition to the recovery
497 of high abundances of the genus *Pseudomonas* at the end of the experiment, the
498 recovery of increased microbial diversity in stage 4 following a reduction in earlier
499 stages indicates a level of resilience in select bacterial groups to elevated styrene loads.

500 It is possible that the lower/milder stepwise styrene loads may have selected for more
501 tolerant or resistant microbes that were able to withstand the greater loads at later
502 stages, similar to results observed in previous studies in gas biofilters and anaerobic
503 digestors degrading other contaminants (Cabrol et al., 2016; De Vrieze et al., 2013;
504 Irvine and Moe, 2001; McMahon et al., 2004).

505 Nutrient limitation is a potential problem in all bioreactor applications during
506 long-scale operation, particularly if the packing material is made of an inorganic
507 substance. Nutrient supplementation is well known to increase bioreactor operational
508 performance, such as increasing removal efficiency and elimination capacity (Chan and
509 Lin, 2006; Morgenroth et al., 1996; Son et al., 2005; Weckhuysen et al., 1993; Yu et al.,
510 2003). Although literature on the effects of nutrient supplementation on both microbial
511 community structure and bioreactor performance is limited, addition of specific
512 nutrients has been shown to affect microbial community diversity while simultaneously
513 increasing removal efficiency (Chen et al., 2009). Nitrogen limitation in particular has
514 been demonstrated to play an important role in biofilm growth. Nitrogen concentrations
515 have been shown to have a greater influence on the mineralization of VOCs such as
516 toluene compared to other nutrients like phosphorus and potassium (Delhoménie et al.,
517 2001). Furthermore, additions of ammonia or nitrate in a biofilter degrading toluene
518 increased the elimination capacity by more than a factor of 10 (Beuger and Gostomski,
519 2009), thus showing a specific beneficial role for nutrients in reactor operational
520 performance. High levels of ammonium detected throughout the experimental stages
521 may have provided a suitable nitrogen source for most bacteria, since the assimilation of
522 ammonia is known to be easier than nitrate in some conventional and trickle-bed air
523 biofilters (Jorio et al., 2000; Song et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2002) In

524 fact, Sempere et al. (2011) showed that addition of ammonia gave better performance
525 results than addition of nitrate for styrene removal in biotrickling filters.

526 Next-generation sequencing (NGS) methods have a distinct advantage over older
527 traditional molecular methods in the characterization of bacterial communities in that a
528 greater amount of information on species abundance can be obtained, especially for
529 non-dominant members. Combinations of pyrosequencing and PCR-DGGE have been
530 simultaneously applied in a recent study examining shifts in bacterial community
531 diversity and composition in response to front aeration in the horizontal subsurface flow
532 constructed wetlands, and similar bacterial diversity was found using both methods
533 (Zhong et al., 2015). Comparison of results from pyrosequencing and DGGE in this
534 study revealed similarities in several dominant bacterial groups. Curiously, no
535 *Pseudomonas* spp. were detected using DGGE, despite a high relative abundance found
536 using pyrosequencing. Furthermore, DGGE analysis further revealed many dominant
537 bacterial species belonging to the phylum Bacteroidetes that were not detected by
538 pyrosequencing. The use of different primers for pyrosequencing and DGGE likely
539 played a role in at least some of the differences in detected taxonomic groups by each
540 respective method. After examination of the reverse primer 907R from Muyzer et al.
541 (1998) used for DGGE analysis in this study, we found a single-base mismatch between
542 the primer and classified sequences assigned to the genus *Pseudomonas* through
543 pyrosequencing (data not shown), thus explaining why *Pseudomonas* may not have
544 been detected using DGGE. These results stress the necessity for careful selection of
545 PCR primers for use in any molecular method for examining microbial communities
546 within bioreactors.

547

548

549 **5 Conclusions**

550 Gradual increases on styrene contaminant loads appear to shape and condition microbial
551 communities to withstand increasing levels of contaminants. In addition, anoxic
552 microenvironments within the heterogeneous biofilm impacted on the relative
553 abundance of some identified styrene degraders such *Brevundimonas* and
554 *Pseudomonas*. It is likely important that a compositionally- and functionally-diverse
555 initial microbial community is provided as the inoculum source since functional
556 redundancy appears to play a major role in maintaining bioreactor performance.
557 Therefore, the use of activated sludge as an inoculum source, which typically contains
558 highly diverse microbial populations, appears to satisfy these requirements and confers
559 several advantages over inoculations with mono- or mixed cultures of bacteria and/or
560 fungi in addition to being less expensive compared to these latter options.

561

562 **6 Acknowledgements**

563 The research leading to these results has received funding from the People Programme
564 (Marie Curie Actions) of the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme
565 FP7/2007-2013/ under REA grant agreement n° 284949. M. C. Pérez would like to
566 acknowledge financial support for her FPU contract (AP20009-2645) from the
567 Ministerio de Educación Cultura y Deporte, Spain. We would like to thank the Unidad
568 de Genómica del Servei Central de Suport a la Investigació Experimental at the
569 Universitat de València for performing the pyrosequencing run and for technical advice
570 in pyrosequencing. We would also like to thank the Centro de Cálculo at the Universitat
571 de València for training and use of supercomputers for data analysis of pyrosequencing.

572

573 **7 References**

- 574 Allison SD, Martiny JB. 2008. Colloquium paper: resistance, resilience, and redundancy
575 in microbial communities. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A 105 Suppl 1:11512-9.
576 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0801925105>
- 577 Altschul SF, Gish W, Miller W, Myers EW, Lipman DJ. 1990. Basic local alignment
578 search tool. J Mol Biol 215:403-410. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836\(05\)80360-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836(05)80360-2)
- 579 Arnold M, Reittu A, von Wright A, Martikainen PJ, Suihko ML. 1997. Bacterial
580 degradation of styrene in waste gases using a peat filter. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol
581 48:738-44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002530051126>
- 582 Ayarza JM, Guerrero LD, Erijman L. 2010. Nonrandom assembly of bacterial
583 populations in activated sludge flocs. Microb Ecol 59:436-44.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-009-9581-1>
- 585 Beltrametti F, Marconi AM, Bestetti G, Colombo C, Galli E, Ruzzi M, Zennaro E.
586 1997. Sequencing and functional analysis of styrene catabolism genes from
587 *Pseudomonas fluorescens* ST. Appl Environ Microbiol 63:2232-9.
- 588 Bergmark L, Poulsen PH, Al-Soud WA, Norman A, Hansen LH, Sorensen SJ. 2012.
589 Assessment of the specificity of *Burkholderia* and *Pseudomonas* qPCR assays for
590 detection of these genera in soil using 454 pyrosequencing. FEMS Microbiol Lett
591 333:77-84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6968.2012.02601.x>
- 592 Beuger A, Gostomski PA. 2009. Development of a biofilter with water content control
593 for research purposes. Chemical Engineering Journal 151:89-96.
594 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2009.01.045>

595 Briones A, Raskin L. 2003. Diversity and dynamics of microbial communities in
596 engineered environments and their implications for process stability. *Curr Opin*
597 *Biotechnol* 14:270-6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-1669\(03\)00065-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-1669(03)00065-X)

598 Cabrol L, Malhautier L, Poly F, Lepeuple AS, Fanlo JL. 2012a. Bacterial dynamics in
599 steady-state biofilters: beyond functional stability. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* 79:260-71.
600 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6941.2011.01213.x>

601 Cabrol L, Malhautier L, Poly F, Roux XL, Lepeuple AS, Fanlo JL. 2012b. Resistance
602 and resilience of removal efficiency and bacterial community structure of gas biofilters
603 exposed to repeated shock loads. *Bioresour Technol* 123:548-57.
604 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2012.07.033>

605 Cabrol L, Malhautier L. 2011. Integrating microbial ecology in bioprocess
606 understanding: the case of gas biofiltration. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 90:837-49.
607 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-011-3191-9>

608 Cabrol L, Poly F, Malhautier L, Pommier T, Lerondelle C, Verstraete W, Lepeuple AS,
609 Fanlo JL, Le Roux X. 2016. Management of microbial communities through transient
610 disturbances enhances the functional resilience of nitrifying gas-biofilters to future
611 disturbances. *Environ Sci Technol* 50:338-48. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b02740>

612 Chan WC, Lin ZY. 2006. A process to prepare a synthetic filter material containing
613 nutrients for biofiltration. *Bioresour Technol* 97:1927-33.
614 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2005.08.005>

615 Chen J, Wang ZY, Jiang YF, Qian HF, Zhang W, Chen JM. 2009. Assessment of the
616 bacterial community for denitrifying removal of nitric oxide in a rotating drum biofilter
617 by denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis. *Environmental Engineering Science* 26.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1089/ees.2008.0153>

619 Cox HH, Moerman RE, van Baalen S, van Heiningen WN, Doddema HJ, Harder W.
620 1997. Performance of a styrene-degrading biofilter containing the yeast *Exophiala*
621 *jeanselmei*. Biotechnol Bioeng 53:259-266. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19970205)53:3%3C259::AID-BIT3%3E3.0.CO;2-H)
622 [0290\(19970205\)53:3%3C259::AID-BIT3%3E3.0.CO;2-H](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19970205)53:3%3C259::AID-BIT3%3E3.0.CO;2-H)

623 De Vrieze J, Verstraete W, Boon N. 2013. Repeated pulse feeding induces functional
624 stability in anaerobic digestion. Microb Biotechnol 6:414-24.
625 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.12025>

626 Delhoménie MC, Bibeau L, Roy S, Brzezinski R, Heitz M. 2001. Influence of nitrogen
627 on the degradation of toluene in a compost-based biofilter. Journal of Chemical
628 Technology and Biotechnology 76:997-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.472>

629 Falk MW, Song KG, Matiasek MG, Wuertz S. 2009. Microbial community dynamics in
630 replicate membrane bioreactors--natural reproducible fluctuations. Water Res 43:842-
631 52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2008.11.021>

632 Feng RF, Xu MY, Li JJ, Huang SB, Zhao G, Tu X, Sun GP, Guo J. 2019. Structure and
633 predictive functional profiling of microbial communities in two biotrickling filters
634 treated with continuous/discontinuous waste gases. AMB Expr 9: 2.
635 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-018-0726-9>

636 Fernandez A, Huang S, Seston S, Xing J, Hickey R, Criddle C, Tiedje J. 1999. How
637 stable is stable? Function versus community composition. Appl Environ Microbiol
638 65:3697-704.

639 Fierer N, Jackson JA, Vilgalys R, Jackson RB. 2005. Assessment of soil microbial
640 community structure by use of taxon-specific quantitative PCR assays. Appl Environ
641 Microbiol 71:4117-20. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.7.4117-4120.2005>

642 Franklin RB, Mills AL. 2006. Structural and functional responses of a sewage microbial
643 community to dilution-induced reductions in diversity. *Microb Ecol* 52:280-8.
644 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-006-9033-0>

645 Hartmans S, Smits JP, van der Werf MJ, Volkering F, de Bont JA. 1989. Metabolism of
646 styrene oxide and 2-phenylethanol in the styrene-degrading *Xanthobacter* strain 124X.
647 *Appl Environ Microbiol* 55:2850-5.

648 Hartmans S, van der Werf MJ, de Bont JA. 1990. Bacterial degradation of styrene
649 involving a novel flavin adenine dinucleotide-dependent styrene monooxygenase. *Appl*
650 *Environ Microbiol* 56:1347-51.

651 Hwang JW, Choi CY, Park S, Lee EY. 2008. Biodegradation of gaseous styrene by
652 *Brevibacillus* sp. using a novel agitating biotrickling filter. *Biotechnol Lett* 30:1207-12.
653 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10529-008-9670-0>

654 Inoue A, Horikoshi K. 1989. A *Pseudomonas putida* thrives in high concentrations of
655 toluene. *Nature* 338:264–266.

656 Iranpour R, Cox H, Deshusses M, Schroeder E. 2005. Literature review of air pollution
657 control biofilters and biotrickling filters for odor and volatile organic compound
658 removal. *Environ Prog Sustain Energy* 24:254-267. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.10077>

659 Irvine RL, Moe WM. 2001. Period biofilter operation for enhanced performance during
660 unsteady-state loading conditions. *Water Sci Technol* 43:231-9.

661 Iwanade A, Jang JH, Hirai M, Shoda M. 2005. Enhancement of styrene removal by
662 *Pseudomonas* sp. SR-5 in mixed culture with a benzoic acid-degrading bacterium in
663 biofilter. *Environ Technol* 26:941-949. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593332608618505>

664 Jang JH, Hirai M, Shoda M. 2004. Styrene degradation by *Pseudomonas* sp. SR-5 in
665 biofilters with organic and inorganic packing materials. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*
666 65:349-55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-004-1628-0>

667 Jang JH, Hirai M, Shoda M. 2005. Performance of a styrene-degrading biofilter
668 inoculated with *Pseudomonas* sp. SR-5. *J Biosci Bioeng* 100:297-302.
669 <https://doi.org/10.1263/jbb.100.297>

670 Jang JH, Hirai M, Shoda M. 2006. Enhancement of styrene removal efficiency in
671 biofilter by mixed cultures of *Pseudomonas* sp. SR-5. *J Biosci Bioeng* 102:53-59.
672 <https://doi.org/10.1263/jbb.102.53>

673 Jorio H, Bibeau L, Heitz M. 2000. Biofiltration of air contaminated by styrene: Effect
674 of nitrogen supply, gas flow rate, and inlet concentration. *Environ Sci Technol* 34:1764-
675 1771. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es990911c>

676 Jung IG, Park CH. 2005. Characteristics of styrene degradation by *Rhodococcus*
677 *pyridinovorans* isolated from a biofilter. *Chemosphere* 61:451-6.
678 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.03.007>

679 Kampfer P, Schulze R, Jackel U, Malik KA, Amann R, Spring S. 2005.
680 *Hydrogenophaga defluvii* sp. nov. and *Hydrogenophaga atypica* sp. nov., isolated from
681 activated sludge. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 55:341-4.
682 <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.03041-0>

683 Kersey PJ, Allen JE, Armean I, Boddu S, Bolt BJ, Carvalho-Silva D, Christensen M,
684 Davis P, Falin LJ, Grabmueller C, Humphrey J, Kerhornou A, Khobova J,
685 Aranganathan NK, Langridge N, Lowy E, McDowall MD, Maheswari U, Nuhn M, Ong
686 CK, Overduin B, Paulini M, Pedro H, Perry E, Spudich G, Tapanari E, Walts B,
687 Williams G, Tello-Ruiz M, Stein J, Wei S, Ware D, Bolser DM, Howe KL, Kulesha E,

688 Lawson D, Maslen G, Staines DM. 2016. Ensembl Genomes 2016: more genomes,
689 more complexity. *Nucleic Acids Res* 44:D574-80. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1209>

690 Liao DQ, Li EZ, Li JJ, Zeng PY, Feng RF, Xu MY, Sun GP. 2018. Removal of
691 benzene, toluene, xylene and styrene by biotrickling filters and identification of their
692 interactions. *Plos One* 13: 1. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189927>

693 Liu Y, Jin JH, Liu HC, Liu ZP. 2013. *Dokdonella immobilis* sp. nov., isolated from a
694 batch reactor for the treatment of triphenylmethane dye effluent. *Int J Syst Evol*
695 *Microbiol* 63:1557-61. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.042002-0>

696 Lu LC, Wang GC, Yeung M, Xi JY, Hu HY. 2018. Response of microbial community
697 structure and metabolic profile to shifts of inlet VOCs in a gas-phase biofilter. *AMB*
698 *Expr* 8: 160. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-018-0687-z>

699 Ma Q, Qu Y, Shen W, Zhang Z, Wang J, Liu Z, Li D, Li H, Zhou J. 2015. Bacterial
700 community compositions of coking wastewater treatment plants in steel industry
701 revealed by Illumina high-throughput sequencing. *Bioresour Technol* 179:436-43.
702 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.12.041>

703 McMahon KD, Zheng D, Stams AJ, Mackie RI, Raskin L. 2004. Microbial population
704 dynamics during start-up and overload conditions of anaerobic digesters treating
705 municipal solid waste and sewage sludge. *Biotechnol Bioeng* 87:823-34.

706 Miura Y, Hiraiwa MN, Ito T, Itonaga T, Watanabe Y, Okabe S. 2007. Bacterial
707 community structures in MBRs treating municipal wastewater: relationship between
708 community stability and reactor performance. *Water Res* 41:627-37.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2006.11.005>

710 Morgenroth E, Schroeder ED, Chang DP, Scow KM. 1996. Nutrient limitation in a
711 compost biofilter degrading hexane. *J Air Waste Manag Assoc* 46:300-308.

712 Muyzer G, Brinkhoff T, Nuebel U, Santegoeds C, Schaefer H, Waver C. 1998.
713 Denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE) in microbial ecology. In Akkermans
714 ADL, van Elsas JD, de Bruijn FJ (ed) *Molecular Microbial Ecology Manual*. Kluwer
715 Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, pp 1-27.

716 Muyzer G, de Waal EC, Uitterlinden AG. 1993. Profiling of complex microbial
717 populations by denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis analysis of polymerase chain
718 reaction-amplified genes coding for 16S rRNA. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 59:695-700.

719 Nadarajah N, Allen DG, Fulthorpe RR. 2007. Effects of transient temperature
720 conditions on the divergence of activated sludge bacterial community structure and
721 function. *Water Res* 41:2563-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.02.002>

722 Okamoto K, Izawa M, Yanase H. 2003. Isolation and application of a styrene-degrading
723 strain of *Pseudomonas putida* to biofiltration. *J Biosci Bioeng* 95:633-6.
724 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-1723\(03\)80176-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-1723(03)80176-7)

725 Oksanen J, Blanchet FG, Kindt R, Legendre P, Minchin PR, O'Hara RB, Simpson GL,
726 Solymos P, Stevens MHH, Wagner H. 2013. *Vegan: community ecology package*. R
727 package version 2.0-10.

728 Pérez MC, Álvarez-Hornos FJ, Portune K, Gabaldón C. 2015. Abatement of styrene
729 waste gas emission by biofilter and biotrickling filter: comparison of packing materials
730 and inoculation procedures. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 99:19-32.
731 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-014-5773-9>

732 Portune KJ, Pérez MC, Álvarez-Hornos FJ, Gabaldón C. 2015. Investigating bacterial
733 populations in styrene-degrading biofilters by 16S rDNA tag pyrosequencing. *Appl*
734 *Microbiol Biotechnol* 99:3-18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-014-5868-3>

735 Qi B, Moe WM, Kinney KA. 2002. Biodegradation of volatile organic compounds by
736 five fungal species. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 58:684-689.
737 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-002-0938-3>

738 Rene ER, Montes M, Veiga MC, Kennes C. 2011. Styrene removal from polluted air in
739 one and two-liquid phase biotrickling filter: steady and transient-state performance and
740 pressure drop control. *Bioresour Technol* 102:6791-6800.
741 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.04.010>

742 Sempere F, Martínez-Soria VM, Palau J, Peña-roja JM, San-Valero P, Gabaldón C.
743 2011. Effects of nitrogen source and empty bed residence time on the removal of
744 styrene gaseous emissions by biotrickling filtration. *Bioprocess Biosyst Eng* 34:859-
745 867. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00449-011-0536-9>

746 Schloss PD, Westcott SL, Ryabin T, Hall JR, Hartmann M, Hollister EB, Lesniewski
747 RA, Oakley BB, Parks DH, Robinson CJ, Sahl JW, Stres B, Thallinger GG, Van Horn
748 DJ, Weber CF. 2009. Introducing mothur: open-source, platform-independent,
749 community-supported software for describing and comparing microbial communities.
750 *Appl Environ Microbiol* 75:7537-7541. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01541-09>

751 Son H, Striebig BA, Regan RW. 2005. Nutrient limitations during the biofiltration of
752 methyl isoamyl ketone. *Environmental Progress* 24:75-81.
753 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.10040>

754 Song J, Ramirez J, Kinney KA. 2003. Nitrogen utilization in a vapor-phase biofilter.
755 *Water Res* 37:4497-505. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(03\)00408-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(03)00408-1)

756 Venables WN, Ripley BD. 2002. Modern applied statistics with S. 4th edition. Springer,
757 New York.

758 Wang C, Xi JY, Hu HY. 2009. Effects of nitrogen source, empty bed residence time and
759 inlet concentration on biofilter removal of chlorobenzene. Eng Life Sci 9:109-115.
760 <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.200800006>

761 Wang Q, Garrity GM, Tiedje JM, Cole JR. 2007. Naive Bayesian classifier for rapid
762 assignment of rRNA sequences into the new bacterial taxonomy. Appl Environ
763 Microbiol 73:5261-7. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00062-07>

764 Warhurst AM, Clarke KF, Hill RA, Holt RA, Fewson CA. 1994. Metabolism of styrene
765 by *Rhodococcus rhodochrous* NCIMB 13259. Appl Environ Microbiol 60:1137-45.

766 Weckhuysen B, Vriens L, Verachtert H. 1993. The effect of nutrient supplementation on
767 the biofiltration removal of butanol in contaminated air. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol
768 39:395-399.

769 Yang H, Minuth B, Allen DG. 2002. Effects of nitrogen and oxygen on biofilter
770 performance. J Air Waste Manag Assoc 52:279-86.
771 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10473289.2002.10470777>

772 Yoon JH, Kang SJ, Ryu SH, Jeon CO, Oh TK. 2008. Hydrogenophaga bisanensis sp.
773 nov., isolated from wastewater of a textile dye works. Int J Syst Evol Microbiol 58:393-
774 7. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.65271-0>

775 Yu X, Zhang XJ, Liu XL, Zhao XD, Wang ZS. 2003. Phosphorus limitation in
776 biofiltration for drinking water treatment. J Environ Sci (China) 15:494-9.

777 Zhong F, Wu J, Dai Y, Yang L, Zhang Z, Cheng S, Zhang Q. 2015. Bacterial
778 community analysis by PCR-DGGE and 454-pyrosequencing of horizontal subsurface

779 flow constructed wetlands with front aeration. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 99:1499-512.

780 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-014-6063-2>

781 Zumstein E, Moletta R, Godon JJ. 2000. Examination of two years of community

782 dynamics in an anaerobic bioreactor using fluorescence polymerase chain reaction

783 (PCR) single-strand conformation polymorphism analysis. *Environ Microbiol* 2:69-78.

784

785

786

787

788

789

790

791

792

793

794

795

796

797

798

799

800

801

802

803

804 **Figure Captions**

805 **Figure 1.** Dendrogram using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity to show the relationship between
806 microbial composition among sampling time points.

807

808 **Figure 2.** Percentage of total bacterial sequences (mean of replicates) assigned to the
809 top 25 most abundant bacterial genera in the 7 sampling time points. Combined
810 percentages of remaining classified genera are labeled as Remaining Genera. Sequences
811 labeled as Unclassified (Phyla), Unclassified (Class), Unclassified (Order), Unclassified
812 (Family) could not be assigned to any classified taxon at each respective taxonomic
813 level using the Ribosomal Database Project Classifier at the selected bootstrap
814 confidence estimate threshold of 50%.

815

816 **Figure 3.** Relative abundances of *Pseudomonas* spp. at each of the 7 sampling time
817 points as represented by the average percent of eubacterial copy number that is assigned
818 to *Pseudomonas* using *Pseudomonas*-specific PCR primers.

819

820 **Figure 4.** DGGE profiles for bacterial 16S rRNA genes at each of the 7 sampling time
821 points. Numbers represent DGGE bands found at determined heights of DNA fragment
822 separation that correspond to dominant species found across time points.

823

824 **Figure 5.** Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) of bacterial community
825 composition with operational conditions. Arrows represent the styrene inlet load and
826 nitrate, magnesium, phosphate and sulfate concentrations of the recirculation solution.
827 Percentages within parentheses on each axis represent the percent of total inertia
828 explained by each axis. Samples at each of the 7 sampling time points are represented

829 by gray squares. Numbers associated with circles represent the top 25 most abundant
830 genera detected over the 7 sampling time points found in Fig. 2.

831

832 **Table 1** Average biotrickling filter performance and operational conditions (mean \pm S.D.). Samples for microbial analysis were taken on days 20,
 833 45, 67, 87, 109, 133, and 155.

Parameter	Start-up Days 0-20	Stage 1 Days 20-45	Stage 2 Days 45-67	Stage 3 Days 67-87	Stage 4 Days 87-109	Stage 5 Days 109-133	Stage 6 Days 133-155
BTF Performance							
EBRT (s)	60	60	60	60	45	45	30
Styrene inlet load (g styrene m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	13.0 \pm 0.8	17.4 \pm 0.7	23.5 \pm 0.8	26.6 \pm 2.3	28.4 \pm 4.0	41.0 \pm 1.2	23.8 \pm 1.2
Styrene inlet concentrations (mg Nm ⁻³)	216 \pm 14	290 \pm 12	391 \pm 13	444 \pm 39	355 \pm 50	512 \pm 15	198 \pm 10
Styrene outlet concentrations (mg Nm ⁻³)	19 \pm 19	31 \pm 22	99 \pm 28	109 \pm 40	64 \pm 10	115 \pm 25	45 \pm 11
Removal Efficiency (%)	91.2 \pm 8.9	89.3 \pm 7.7	74.7 \pm 6.4	75.5 \pm 8.0	82.0 \pm 4.2	77.5 \pm 4.8	77.3 \pm 5.8
Styrene Elimination Capacity (g styrene m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	11.8 \pm 1.4	15.5 \pm 1.6	17.5 \pm 1.2	20.1 \pm 2.3	23.3 \pm 4.3	31.8 \pm 2.1	18.4 \pm 1.8
Recirculation Solution							
pH	8.28 \pm 0.62	8.25 \pm 0.32	8.12 \pm 0.37	7.97 \pm 0.45	8.06 \pm 0.51	7.51 \pm 0.70	8.09 \pm 0.22
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	99.1 \pm 34.1	2.6 \pm 0.3	0.7 \pm 0.2	0.9 \pm 0.1	1.1 \pm 0.3	1.8 \pm 0.5	1.9 \pm 0.3
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	20.7 \pm 4.1	31.3 \pm 4.4	67.4 \pm 12.5	24.0 \pm 6.0	30.0 \pm 7.3	60.8 \pm 12.7	69.9 \pm 7.8
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	65.4 \pm 15.8	75.8 \pm 15.5	107.0 \pm 17.8	90.4 \pm 23.4	112.5 \pm 25.5	147.3 \pm 36.3	319.9 \pm 15.2
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	68.6 \pm 20.0	50.6 \pm 17.6	28.0 \pm 8.7	7.9 \pm 2.7	4.7 \pm 0.6	24.9 \pm 6.1	58.4 \pm 13.4

Na ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	771 ± 170.2	1232 ± 110.4	1205 ± 49.9	1310 ± 47.3	1683 ± 79.2	1793 ± 127.6	2338 ± 168.6
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	859 ± 194.8	1588 ± 119.1	1323 ± 95.3	1756 ± 170.9	2170 ± 151.9	2683 ± 117.5	3088 ± 68.0
K ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	8.7 ± 5.7	31.3 ± 4.63	64.1 ± 6.7	75.7 ± 18.5	107.5 ± 22.3	102.6 ± 9.3	174.7 ± 35.2
Ca ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	23.4 ± 13.4	3.5 ± 0.8	2.0 ± 0.8	2.1 ± 0.9	0.7 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.7
Mg ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	7.0 ± 3.5	0.2 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.2	2.0 ± 0.8	3.0 ± 0.6
% VSS ^a	76.9 ± 1.8	79.3 ± 1.1	80.7 ± 2.4	88.1 ± 2.5	85.7 ± 3.9	83.6 ± 1.6	86.7 ± 2.3

834 ^a(Volatile suspended solids)

835

836

837

838

839

840

841

842

843

844

845 **Table 2** Summary of raw and processed sequences from 454 pyrosequencing, including richness estimators (Observed OTUs), species diversity
 846 indices (Inverse Simpson and Shannon's Diversity) and evenness from samples for each of the 7 sampling time points.

Operational Stage	Sample	Raw reads	Sequences post-processing	Normalized sequences	OTUs ^a	Inverse Simpson (1/D)	Shannon Diversity (H')	Evenness (J')
-	20 days	12,032	11,778	10,464	377	11.8 (11.4-12.2) ^b	3.44 (3.40-3.47) ^b	0.580
1	45 days	14,932	14,119	10,464	376	33.7 (32.7-34.8) ^b	4.17 (4.14-4.19) ^b	0.703
2	67 days	15,708	14,197	10,464	378	5.6 (5.4-5.8) ^b	3.11 (3.06-3.15) ^b	0.524
3	87 days	11,468	10,531	10,464	272	7.7 (7.4-7.9) ^b	2.99 (2.95-3.02) ^b	0.533
4	109 days	11,854	11,105	10,464	268	8.1 (7.8-8.5) ^b	3.07 (3.03-3.10) ^b	0.548
5	133 days	10,990	10,464	10,464	257	13.5 (13.1-13.8) ^b	3.28 (3.24-3.31) ^b	0.590
6	155 days	11,261	10,876	10,464	293	15.1 (14.7-15.5) ^b	3.36 (3.33-3.39) ^b	0.591

847

848 ^a(Operational taxonomic units observed after normalization)

849 ^b(95% confidence intervals of respective estimators shown in parentheses)

850

Figure1

Figure3

Figure4

Figure5

